

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE IN DESCRIBING ERGONYM

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Abstract: This study looks at how ergonyms are described in English and Uzbek, emphasizing language structures, semantic traits, and cultural factors. It highlights the importance of ergonyms in cross-linguistic and sociocultural contexts by examining parallels and discrepancies in their creation, adaption, and usage.

Keywords: ergonyms, culture, language units, speeches, buildings, organization

Introduction. The rapid urbanization of society and the intensification of intercultural interactions have contributed to the development of city centers and laid the foundation for the emergence of metropolises. As a result, in densely populated areas, the number of enterprises, institutions, and facilities essential for daily life—such as shops, schools, educational centers, hotels, hospitals, cinemas, restaurants, stadiums, banks, and other organizations—has significantly increased. These structures have also begun to form internal networks. The task of selecting appropriate names for these organizations has become an important issue related to linguistics and social matters. Consequently, the naming process has gained great significance and has encouraged the formation of naming services as a dynamic and promising field for society and marketing management.

To describe and determine the foundations of ergonymic structures that operate in two languages, it is crucial to consider the historical, economic, and linguistic-cultural differences, as well as the general similarities between these languages. Conducting a typological analysis of relevant linguistic situations is essential for the comparative study of these ergonymic systems. Furthermore, it is necessary to identify the periods of societal change that have influenced the development of ergonymic structures in various directions.

According to Mechkovskaya, the linguistic situation is generally described as a set of language units consisting of languages and their variants that serve a particular society (an ethnic group or a multinational community) within a specific territory, political-administrative unit, or state. In other words, language units in certain regions are perceived as a system that ensures the continuous process of communication. Several aspects are taken into account when linguistically describing language conditions, including the number of languages (components), their level of participation in society (balanced or unbalanced), their legal status, prestige, balance, and the degree of their interrelatedness.

In Uzbekistan, the reflection of Uzbek-language ergonymic structures demonstrates an increasing influence of foreign languages, indirectly revealing a transition to multilingualism. The presence of English, Russian, Turkish, and Arabic ergonyms is growing. For example, in Tashkent: *Beautiful Salon* (beauty salon), *Virgin Fitness* (fitness center), *Cambridge School* (international school); in Samarkand: *Дворец культуры* (Palace of Culture), *Супермаркет Корзинка* (modern shopping complex), *Плов Хаус* (Plov House – traditional food center); in Bukhara: *Al-Fayruz* (jewelry store), *Sofra* (Turkish restaurant).

Data and Analysis. This phenomenon is not a direct result of a targeted language policy but rather a natural consequence of the linguistic situation following its own laws of development. Consequently, some languages have naturally risen to the level of interethnic communication languages. In this context, Russian and English have historically held such a status due to their widespread use. However, despite Uzbek being the primary language of the Muslim population in Uzbekistan, the number of Arabic ergonyms associated with Arabic culture is increasing. These ergonyms represent a specific sector related to Muslim cultural attributes (clothing, jewelry, furniture, food) and possess significant pragmatic potential.

Conclusion. Many business names in Uzbek, especially in large cities like Tashkent, prefer to use English words or phrases in their names to appear modern or international. For example, *Qahva Vaqti* (Coffee Time) and *Moda Uy* (Fashion House). Studying the naming traditions, motivations, and styles of businesses and other corporate groups allows for the identification of not only their general characteristics but also the unique features of the region in which they are established. This is significant not only for linguistics but also for understanding regional and cultural characteristics.

An ergonym is unique because it embodies the hidden intentions of the name giver or the organization's owner, conveying a specific message. It can be interpreted as part of a speech act, a linguistic sign, or even a conceptual unit. However, although an ergonym possesses form and content like a linguistic sign, these aspects are not entirely identical. This is particularly relevant when an ergonym encompasses multiple meanings, as it does not automatically transform into a specific idea.

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